

Chemistry of Benzoquinoline: Part III

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1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-derivative of Combes' base has been synthesised and oxidised to 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid.

Partial degradation of Combes' base has been reported in earlier papers.^{1,2} The complete degradation of this base by oxidation of its tetrahydro derivative is now described. An earlier attempt³ to degrade the base by oxidation had failed and hence the tetrahydro derivative was selected for the present work.

The 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro compound (I) obtained from Combes' base (*vide infra*) was benzoylated to give the N-benzoyl derivative (II), which was oxidised with potassium permanganate. The intermediate product of oxidation was not isolated but it might be

(I) R=H; R'=R''=CH₃.

(II) R=CO.C₆H₅; R'=R''=CH₃.

(V) R=R'=R''=H.

(III) R=COC₆H₅.

(IV) R=H.

represented by structure (III), since hydrolysis of the product of oxidation gave benzoic acid and 3-amino-2-naphthoic acid (IV). Oxalic acid would possibly be a side-product but its isolation was not attempted. The oxidation thus proceeded normally, and the results established the linear structure of Combes' base. This observation is, however, different from an earlier report⁴ that ring contraction occurs when N-benzoyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline is oxidised with potassium permanganate, the product being N-benzoyl isatin.

The 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro derivative (I) (brown-yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 57-58°) was obtained by reducing Combes' base with tin and hydrochloric acid. Since benzo(g)quinoline on similar reduction⁵ gives (V), there could be little doubt regarding structure (I). However, in order to establish that it was pyridine portion which had undergone

1. Nityanand Singh and A. B. Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 352.

2. A. B. Lal and Nityanand Singh, *Ber.*, 1965, 98, 2427.

3. W. S. Johnson and F. J. Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 210.

4. C. Schotten, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 772.

5. J. V. Braun and H. Gruber, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 1715.

reduction, compound (VII) was synthesised by condensation of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine with acetylacetone and cyclisation of the resultant anil (VI). This base which is a liquid was also obtained from the tetrahydroamine by the Doebner von Miller reaction using paraldehyde and acetone. The picrates from both sources on admixture did not show any depression of melting point. On dehydrogenation with palladium on charcoal, a product was obtained which had melting point 71-73°. This was the low-melting form³ of Combes' base as found by mixed melting point determination with an authentic specimen. Thus in accordance with previous work^{3,6}, the Doebner von Miller reaction with 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine gave the linear benzoquinoline derivative and not the angular base (VIII). This incidently indicated that Reed's base⁷ must have an angular structure (IX), since it was prepared from 2-naphthylamine.

(VI)

(VII)

Compound (VII) on oxidation with potassium permanganate failed to give the expected dicarboxylic acid (X). However, the oxidation product was an extremely hygroscopic carboxylic acid with a basic centre. It could not be purified and attempts to establish its structure were abandoned, but it appeared that this acid was not similar to (X). The oxidation of (VII) with potassium permanganate had probably caused a complete disintegration of the molecule and under controlled condition useful results might be obtained.

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

EXPERIMENTAL*

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine.—2-Naphthylamine (100 g.) was reduced⁸ by sodium and amyl alcohol in batches of 20 g. and the 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine, obtained as carbonate by passing CO₂, was filtered. The filtrate was evaporated leaving a dark viscous oil (20 g.). This was allowed to stand over concentrated HCl (25ml.) for 24 hr. and the crystalline solid collected. They were suspended in water and treated with slight excess of NaOH solution. The light-brown oil liberated was taken up in ether, washed

*All m. p. s. and b. p. s. are uncorrected.

6. J. Lindner and M. Stauffer, *Monatsh.*, 1925, 46, 239.

7. Reed, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1887, [2], 35, 298.

8. E. H. B. Waser and H. Mollering, *Org. Synthesis*, 1929, 9, 85.

and dried (K_2SO_4). Removal of ether and distillation afforded a viscous liquid ($\sim 8g.$) b.p. 120-25°/5mm. (Bamberger and Kitchelt⁹ give b.p. 275-77°/713mm.).

The *picrate* was obtained in benzene and recrystallised from benzene-ethylacetate solution. It had m.p. 184-5°. (Found: C, 51.45; H, 4.32. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4O_7$ requires C, 51.06; H, 4.62%.)

The *hydrochloride* was recrystallised from ethylacetate, and had m.p. 187-8°. (Found: C, 61.64; H, 8.75. $C_{10}H_{14}NCl$, $1/2 H_2O$ requires C, 62.18; H, 7.77%.)

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethylbenzo(g)quinoline (I).—2,4-Dimethylbenzo (g) quinoline (2 g.) was dissolved in concentrated HCl (60 ml.) but the hydrochloride separated after some time. Small pieces of tin foil (7 g.) was added to the mixture, which was stirred for some time, allowed to stand overnight and filtered. The solid was collected, suspended in water and the mixture made alkaline with caustic soda solution. The tetrahydro base was obtained as an oil, which was extracted with ether, washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of ether left a viscous liquid which solidified on washing with a little petroleum. The base was obtained as brownish-yellow flakes (1.55 g.) (from petroleum ether, b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 57-58°. (Found: C, 84.53; H, 8.53. $C_{13}H_{17}N$ requires C, 85.26; H, 8.11%.)

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoylbenzo(g)quinoline (II).—The above base (1g., 1 mol.) and NaOH (0.25g., 1.3 mol.) were taken up in water (4 ml.) and slightly warmed. The mixture was then allowed to cool and benzoyl chloride (0.7 g.) added with shaking. The N-benzoyl derivative which separated as yellow solid was filtered and washed. It furnished yellow silky needles (0.96g.) (from petroleum ether, b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 110.5°. (Found: C, 76.64; H, 6.64. $C_{28}H_{31}NO$. $1\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 77.16; H, 7.01%.)

Oxidation of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dimethyl-N-benzoylbenzo(g)quinoline (II).—The base (II) (0.3g.) was dissolved in acetone (50 ml.) and cooled to 2°C. Finely powdered $KMnO_4$ (0.5g.) was added to it in portions, with stirring during 15 min. The stirring was continued for another 30 min. The mixture was allowed to stand for 48 hr. at 20-22°C. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with acetone and suspended in alcohol (35 ml.). Then moderately strong H_2SO_4 (1.2ml., 1:1) was added, the mixture shaken and allowed to stand for 2 hr. The solid residue was filtered, the filtrate evaporated (reduced pressure) and then refluxed with dil. H_2SO_4 (24 ml.) for 2½ hr. The turbid solution thus obtained was extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was then taken and the acid neutralised with small excess of Na_2CO_3 . 3-Amino-2-Naphthoic acid (IV) was deposited as dirty white substance (0.075 g.) on allowing the solution to stand overnight. This was filtered, crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 213-14°. It gave a positive test for amino and carboxylic groups. On admixture with authentic specimen, m.p. was not depressed.

4-[2-(6, 6,7,8-Tetrahydronaphthylimino)]pentan-2-one (VI).—A mixture of acetylacetone (5 ml.) and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine (4.38 g.) was heated on water bath for 4 hr. The resulting brown viscous liquid was distilled to give a thick yellow oil (6.4g.) b.p. 190-93°/6 mm.

The *picrate* was prepared by mixing a saturated solution of picric acid in benzene. Recrystallised from ethylacetate and benzene, it had m.p. 192-93°. (Found: C, 53.23; H, 4.87. $C_{21}H_{22}N_4O_8 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 52.94; H, 5.04%.)

2,4-Dimethyl-6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-benzo(g)quinoline (VII).—

Method A (Doebner-Miller reaction): Paraldehyde (12 g.) and acetone (20 g.) were saturated with dry HCl and allowed to stand for 24 hr. with exclusion of moisture. This was added in small portions with stirring to a solution of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-naphthylamine (7.69g.) dissolved in conc. HCl (40 ml.) The mixture was then refluxed for 1 hr. on water bath, cooled and made alkaline with NaOH solution. A brown oil was liberated, which was taken up in ether washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue obtained on removal of the ether was dissolved in excess of conc. HCl, filtered and the filtrate diazotised at 0°C, extracted with ether to remove the nitroso compounds and then made alkaline with caustic soda solution. A brown oil separated, which was taken up in ether, washed and dried (CaCl_2). The residue obtained after removal of the ether was distilled to furnish thick yellow oil (2 g.), b.p. 160-64°/3mm.

The *picrate* was prepared by mixing alcoholic solutions of the base and picric acid. Recrystallised from alcohol, it had m.p. 227.5°. (Found: N, 11.49. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_5$ requires N, 11.52%.)

Method B (Combes' reaction): The anil (VI, 6 g.) was added dropwise with stirring to conc. H_2SO_4 cooled below 0°C (ice-salt). The mixture was then heated up to 60° for 2 minutes on water bath and then cooled, slowly poured over ice (100 g.), made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution, extracted with ether, washed and dried (Na_2SO_4). The brown oil obtained on removal of ether was distilled to yield a viscous liquid (6 g.), b.p. 170-75°, 5 mm.

The *picrate* prepared as in method A had m.p. 227-28°C. (Found: C, 57.64; H, 4.98. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7$ requires C, 57.27; H, 4.54%). On admixture of the two *picrates*, the melting point was 228°C.

Dehydrogenation of 2,4-Dimethyl-6,7,8,9-tetrahydrobenzo (g) quinoline (VII).— Palladised charcoal (0.2 g., 10%) was mixed with the tetrahydro base (VII, 1.439 g.) in a tube with two side arms and fitted with a cold finger. The mixture was heated in a metal bath for 5 hours at 175-80° in a current of CO_2 . 2,4-Dimethylbenzo(g) quinoline was deposited on the surface of the cold finger as white needles. These were separated and recrystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 71-73°.

The *picrate* was prepared and crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 265-67° (decomp.) with previous blackening, in a preheated bath at 250°C. following Johnson's⁸ procedure. On admixture with authentic specimen, it had m.p. 266°.

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